

THE DYNAMIC STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS FOR SEMI-INFINITE CRACKS IN ORTHOTROPIC MATERIALS

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Abstract

A method for analyzing the elastodynamic response of an infinite orthotropic material with a semi-infinite crack under impact loads is presented. Uniform loading for three loading modes is considered, i.e. opening, in-plane shear and antiplane shear, and solution for the stress intensity factor history around the crack tip is found. Laplace and Fourier transforms along with the Wiener-Hopf technique are employed to solve the displacement formulation of the equations of motion. The asymptotic expression for the stress near the crack tip is analyzed which lead to a closed-form solution of the dynamic stress intensity factor for each loading mode. It is found that the stress intensity factors are proportional to the square root of time as expected. Results for orthotropic materials are shown to converge to known solutions for isotropic materials derived independently.

Keywords

semi-infinite crack, stress intensity factor, dynamic fracture, orthotropic materials.

1 Introduction

Several problems have been examined in dynamic fracture mechanics for isotropic materials. In fact, there are many closed form solutions for stationary and propagating cracks in isotropic materials under dynamic loading [1, 2]. For orthotropic materials the available solutions are fewer in number, *finite* cracks under impact loading have been analyzed in [3, 7] and in [6] using integral transform methods. These authors reduce their problems to a Fredholm integral equation in the Laplace transform domain which is solved numerically. The stress intensity factor is recovered in the time domain by numerical Laplace inversion

of this solution. With the growing use of composites in many engineering applications it is desirable to have a method for deriving closed form solutions for fundamental problems in cracked orthotropic materials. The semi-infinite crack is a fundamental problem because cracks under dynamic loads can usually be considered semi-infinite for a short duration of time immediately after loading. In the present work a method for analyzing the semi-infinite crack problem under impact loads in orthotropic materials is presented. A closed form solution for the dynamic stress intensity factor is obtained for uniform crack face loading under each loading mode, i.e. opening, in-plane shear and antiplane shear, however, the method can be applied to more general loading including point loads. Laplace and Fourier transforms are applied to the displacement equations of motion and combined with the Wiener-Hopf technique to find expressions for the stress ahead of the crack tip and the displacements on the crack faces. Asymptotic analysis of the stress near the crack tip leads to expressions for the stress intensity factors $K_I(t)$, $K_{II}(t)$, and $K_{III}(t)$.

1.1 Governing Equations, in-plane problems

Consider the plane problem of an infinite orthotropic medium containing a semi-infinite crack, Fig. 1. Let E_i , μ_{ij} and ν_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$) be the engineering elastic constants of the material where the indices 1, 2, and 3 correspond to Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) chosen to coincide with the axes of material orthotropy. The crack faces are along the negative x -axis and the origin of the xy axes is the crack tip. Uniform tractions are applied to the crack faces in directions depending upon the problem considered.

Figure 1: *Schematic of the semi-infinite crack geometry. (a) Normal loading, (b) In-plane shear loading, (c) Antiplane shear loading.*

Restricting the problem to two dimensions with wave propagation limited to the $x - y$ plane by setting all the derivatives with respect to z to be zero, it is readily shown that the displacement equations of motion [4] reduce to

$$c_{11} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + (1 + c_{12}) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} = \frac{1}{c_s^2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + c_{22} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + (1 + c_{12}) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} = \frac{1}{c_s^2} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2}, \quad (2)$$

where u and v are the x and y components of the displacement vector and c_{11} , c_{12} and c_{22}

are non-dimensional parameters related to the elastic constants by the relations:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{11} &= \frac{E_1}{\mu_{12}[1 - (E_2/E_1)\nu_{12}^2]}, \\ c_{22} &= (E_2/E_1)c_{11}, \\ c_{12} &= \nu_{12}c_{22} = \nu_{21}c_{11}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

for generalized plane stress, and by

$$\begin{aligned} c_{11} &= \frac{E_1}{\mu_{12}\Delta}(1 - \nu_{23}\nu_{32}), \\ c_{22} &= \frac{E_2}{\mu_{12}\Delta}(1 - \nu_{13}\nu_{31}), \\ c_{12} &= \frac{E_1}{\mu_{12}\Delta}(\nu_{21} + \frac{E_2}{E_1}\nu_{13}\nu_{32}), \\ \Delta &= 1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21} - \nu_{23}\nu_{32} - \nu_{31}\nu_{13} - \nu_{12}\nu_{23}\nu_{31} - \nu_{13}\nu_{21}\nu_{32}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

for plane strain. In the orthotropic solid, $c_s = \sqrt{\mu_{12}/\rho}$ represents the velocity of the in-plane shear wave propagating along the the principal material axes and ρ is the mass density.

2 Normal Impact

In the case of normal tractions to the crack faces, Fig. 1(a), a spatially uniform pressure of magnitude σ_0 is assumed to be suddenly applied at $t = 0$. Exploiting symmetry and taking only the upper half plane $y \geq 0$, the corresponding boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y(x, 0, t) &= -\sigma_0 H(t) \quad \text{for} \quad -\infty < x < 0, \\ \tau_{xy}(x, 0, t) &= 0 \quad \text{for} \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \\ v(x, 0, t) &= 0 \quad \text{for} \quad x > 0, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $H(t)$ is the Heaviside step function. In addition, the conditions of zero displacements at infinity and zero initial conditions are assumed.

Application of Laplace transform in time and Fourier transform in x to the equations of motion, and enforcing the second boundary condition (5) it is shown that the transformed components of displacement and normal stress are

$$v^*(x, y, p) = \frac{-i}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\alpha_1 e^{-\gamma_1 y} - \beta_1 \alpha_2 e^{-\gamma_2 y}) \frac{A_1(s, p)}{s} e^{-isx} ds, \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_y^* = \frac{-i\mu_{12}}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [(c_{12}s^2 - \alpha_1\gamma_1c_{22})e^{-\gamma_1 y} - (c_{12}s^2 - \alpha_2\gamma_2c_{22})\beta_1 e^{-\gamma_2 y}] \frac{A_1(s, p)}{s} e^{-isx} ds, \quad (7)$$

where

$$\beta_1 = \frac{\alpha_1 + \gamma_1}{\alpha_2 + \gamma_2}, \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_j(s, p) = \frac{c_{11}s^2 + p^2/c_s^2 - \gamma_j^2}{(1 + c_{12})\gamma_j}, \quad j = 1, 2 \quad (9)$$

with γ_1^2 and γ_2^2 being two distinct roots of the quadratic equation

$$c_{22}\gamma^4 + [(c_{12}^2 + 2c_{12} - c_{11}c_{22})s^2 - (1 + c_{22})p^2/c_s^2]\gamma^2 + (c_{11}s^2 + p^2/c_s^2)(s^2 + p^2/c_s^2) = 0. \quad (10)$$

Introducing the functions

$$E(s, p) = \frac{1}{s}(\alpha_1 - \beta_1\alpha_2)A_1(s, p), \quad (11)$$

$$F(s, p) = -\frac{\sqrt{s^2 + p^2/c_d^2}}{(\alpha_1 - \beta_1\alpha_2)\xi}[c_{12}s^2 - \alpha_1\gamma_1c_{22} - \beta_1(c_{12}s^2 - \alpha_2\gamma_2c_{22})], \quad (12)$$

$$\xi = \frac{-1}{c_{11}(1 + c_{12})(N_1 + N_2)}\{(c_{12}^2 + c_{12} - c_{11}c_{22})(c_{12}N_1N_2 - c_{11}) - c_{22}[c_{12}N_1^2N_2^2 + c_{11}(N_1^2 + N_1N_2 + N_2^2)]\}, \quad (13)$$

$$N_{1,2}^2 = \frac{1}{2c_{22}}\{c_{11}c_{22} - c_{12}^2 - 2c_{12} \pm [(c_{11}c_{22} - c_{12}^2 - 2c_{12})^2 - 4c_{11}c_{22}]^{1/2}\}, \quad (14)$$

where the velocity $c_d = \sqrt{c_{11}c_s}$ represents the dilatational wave speed along the x -axis and in view of the first and third boundary conditions in (5), equations (6) and (7) yield the following pair of dual integral equations for the determination of the function $E(s, p)$

$$\frac{i\mu_{12}\xi}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{F(s, p)}{\sqrt{s^2 + p^2/c_d^2}} E(s, p)e^{-isx} ds = -\frac{\sigma_0}{p}H(-x) + \sigma_+^*(x, p), \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{-i}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E(s, p)e^{-isx} ds = v_-^*(x, p), \quad (16)$$

and by Fourier transform inversion

$$i\mu_{12}\xi \frac{F(s, p)}{\sqrt{s^2 + p^2/c_d^2}} E(s, p) = -\frac{\sigma_0}{pis} + \Sigma_+(s), \quad (17)$$

$$-iE(s, p) = V_-(s), \quad (18)$$

where $\Sigma_+(s)$ and $V_-(s)$ are the double transform of the stress ahead of the crack tip and the displacement of the cracks faces respectively.

It can be shown that $\Sigma_+(s)$ and $V_-(s)$ will be analytic in $\text{Im}(s) > -p/c_d$ and $\text{Im}(s) < 0$ respectively [5].

2.1 Wiener-Hopf technique

Eliminating $E(s, p)$ from (17) and (18) yields a Wiener-Hopf equation

$$\frac{\sigma_0}{ips} - \Sigma_+(s) = \mu_{12}\xi \frac{F(s, p)}{\sqrt{s^2 + p^2/c_d^2}} V_-(s) \quad (19)$$

which contains only the two unknown functions $\Sigma_+(s)$ and $V_-(s)$, and now the Wiener-Hopf technique can be applied as follows. Suppose that the functions $L(s)$ and $D(s)$ are defined and factored as

$$L(s) = \frac{L_-(s)}{L_+(s)} = \mu_{12}\xi \frac{F(s, p)}{\sqrt{s^2 + p^2/c_d^2}}, \quad \frac{\sigma_0}{ips} L_+(s) = D(s) = D_+(s) + D_-(s) \quad (20)$$

then equation (19) becomes

$$D_+(s) - \Sigma_+(s)L_+(s) = L_-(s)V_-(s) - D_-(s) = W(s). \quad (21)$$

The first member of this equation is analytic in the upper half of the s -plane $\text{Im}(s) > -p/c_d$ and the second member is analytic in the lower half of the s -plane $\text{Im}(s) < 0$. Therefore the regions of analyticity overlap.

The only zeros of $F(s, p)$ are of the form $\pm ip/c_R$ where c_R is the Rayleigh wave speed [8].

Figure 2: Branch cuts for $\hat{F}(s)$ in the s -plane.

The first step in factoring $L(s)$ is to define

$$\hat{F}(s) = \frac{F(s, p)}{s^2 + p^2/c_R^2} \quad (22)$$

thus $\hat{F}(s) \rightarrow 1$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$, (the constant ξ in (12) was chosen to make this possible). The function $\hat{F}(s)$ is regular and $\hat{F}(s) \neq 0$ in the s -plane cut as shown in Fig. 2. The only singularities are the branch points shared with γ_1 and γ_2 . It is readily shown that the branch points of γ_1 and γ_2 are $s = \pm \frac{ip}{c_s}$ and $s = \frac{ip}{\sqrt{c_{11}} c_s} = \pm \frac{ip}{c_d}$ respectively.

It is well-known that factorization is accomplished most directly for functions that approach unity as $|s| \rightarrow \infty$ and that have neither zeros nor poles in the finite plane; $\hat{F}(s)$ is an example of such a function. Therefore, using Cauchy's integral formula it can be shown that [2]

$$\hat{F}_{\pm}(s) = \exp \left\{ \frac{-1}{\pi} \int_{1/c_d}^{1/c_s} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\text{Im}[\hat{F}(ipw)]}{\text{Re}[\hat{F}(ipw)]} \right) \frac{dw}{w \mp \frac{is}{p}} \right\}. \quad (23)$$

Returning to the factorization of $L(s)$ it is found that

$$L_+(s) = \frac{\sqrt{s + ip/c_d}}{(s + ip/c_R) \hat{F}_+(s)}, \quad L_-(s) = \mu_{12} \xi \frac{(s - ip/c_R)}{\sqrt{s - ip/c_d}} \hat{F}_-(s). \quad (24)$$

Decomposition of $D(s)$ follows easily,

$$D_+(s) = \frac{\sigma_0}{p} \left[\frac{L_+(s) - L_+(0)}{is} \right], \quad D_-(s) = \frac{\sigma_0}{p} \left[\frac{L_+(0)}{is} \right]. \quad (25)$$

Each side of equation (21) is analytic in one of the overlapping half planes, and the sides coincide on the strip of overlap. Using the Liouville's theorem it possible to prove that $W(s) = 0$ [5], hence, solutions for $\Sigma_+(s)$ and $V_-(s)$ can be found as

$$\Sigma_+(s) = \frac{D_+(s)}{L_+(s)} = -\frac{\sigma_0}{p} \frac{1}{is} \left[\frac{L_+(0)}{L_+(s)} - 1 \right], \quad (26)$$

$$V_-(s) = \frac{D_-(s)}{L_-(s)} = \frac{\sigma_0}{p} \frac{1}{is} \frac{L_+(0)}{L_-(s)}. \quad (27)$$

2.2 Stress Intensity factor

To find the stress intensity factor, an asymptotic expression for the normal stress near the crack tip is sought. Combining Abel's theorem which relates asymptotic expressions between a function and its Fourier transform and the definition of stress intensity factor we get

$$K_I^*(p) = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \sqrt{2\pi x} \sigma_+^*(x, p) = \lim_{s \rightarrow +\infty} e^{-i\pi/4} \sqrt{2s} \Sigma_+(s). \quad (28)$$

Clearly, the behavior of $\Sigma_+(s)$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$ is needed, i.e.

$$\Sigma_+(s) = \frac{-\sigma_0}{(ip)^{3/2}} \frac{1}{s^{1/2}} \frac{p}{\sqrt{c_d} \sqrt{F(0, p)}} \quad \text{as } s \rightarrow \infty. \quad (29)$$

so that

$$K_I^*(p) = \sigma_0 \sqrt{\frac{2c_s \xi}{\sqrt{c_{22}}}} \frac{1}{p^{3/2}}, \quad (30)$$

and by Laplace inversion the dynamic stress intensity factor in the time domain for this loading mode is

$$K_I(t) = 2\sigma_0 \sqrt{\frac{2c_s \xi}{\pi \sqrt{c_{22}}}} \sqrt{t}. \quad (31)$$

For the isotropic case and with plane strain conditions, substituting $E_1 = E_2 = E$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = \nu$ and $\mu_{12} = E/2(1 + \nu)$ in equations (4) and the results in (13) it is found that $c_{22} = 2(1 - \nu)/(1 - 2\nu)$ and $\xi = 1/(1 - \nu)$ and equation (31) reduces to the well known result for isotropic materials [2]

$$K_I(t) = 2\sigma_0 \frac{\sqrt{c_d(1 - 2\nu)/\pi}}{(1 - \nu)} \sqrt{t}.$$

3 In-Plane Shear Loading

Consider the crack geometry illustrated in figure 1(b). The crack faces are subjected to suddenly applied, spatially uniform shear traction of magnitude τ_0 . Exploiting asymmetry and examining the half space $y \geq 0$, the corresponding boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{xy}(x, 0, t) &= -\tau_0 H(t) \quad \text{for } -\infty < x < 0, \\ \sigma_y(x, 0, t) &= 0 \quad \text{for } -\infty < x < \infty, \\ u(x, 0, t) &= 0 \quad \text{for } x > 0,\end{aligned}\tag{32}$$

where $H(t)$ is the Heaviside step function. In addition, the condition of zero displacements at infinity and zero initial conditions are assumed.

The method of solution is similar to that used for normal impact. Using Laplace and Fourier transform and the Wiener-Hopf technique an expression for the double transform of the stress ahead of the crack tip can be found and its asymptotic behavior leads to the dynamic stress intensity factor for mode II. That is,

$$K_{II}(t) = 2\tau_0 \sqrt{2c_s \eta / \pi} \sqrt{t}.\tag{33}$$

For the isotropic case and with plane strain conditions $\eta = 1/(1 - \nu)$ and equation (33) reduces to the well known result for isotropic materials [2]

$$K_{II}(t) = 2\tau_0 \sqrt{\frac{2c_s}{\pi(1 - \nu)}} \sqrt{t}.$$

4 Antiplane Shear

Consider a semi-infinite crack in orthotropic material shown in Fig. 1(c), subjected to antiplane shear loading of magnitude τ_0 . The governing differential equation for two dimensional antiplane motions of homogeneous, orthotropic, linearly elastic solids is [4]

$$\beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = \frac{1}{c_h^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2},\tag{34}$$

where

$$\beta^2 = \frac{C_{55}}{C_{44}} \quad \text{and} \quad c_h = \sqrt{C_{44}/\rho}.$$

Again, the principal material axes of orthotropy are chosen to coincide with the (x, y, z) axes, such that the in-plane and antiplane motions are not coupled. In terms of the engineering constants, C_{44} and C_{55} are given by $C_{44} = \mu_{23}$ and $C_{55} = \mu_{31}$. The non-zero stresses are related to the displacements by the equations

$$\tau_{xz} = C_{55} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \quad \tau_{yz} = C_{44} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}.\tag{35}$$

Exploiting symmetry and examining the upper half-plane $y \geq 0$, the boundary conditions for this loading mode are given as

$$\tau_{yz}(x, 0, t) = -\tau_0 H(t) \quad \text{for } x < 0 \quad (36)$$

$$w(x, 0, t) = 0 \quad \text{for } x > 0. \quad (37)$$

The method of solution is very similar to that used for the in-plane problems. Applying Laplace and Fourier transforms and the Wiener-Hopf technique, the dynamic stress intensity factor for mode III, i.e.

$$K_{III}(t) = 2\tau_0 \sqrt{2\beta c_h / \pi} \sqrt{t}. \quad (38)$$

For transversely isotropic materials with fibers along the x -axis, $C_{55} = \mu_{12}$ and $\beta c_h = \sqrt{\mu_{12}/\rho} = c_s$, this equation becomes

$$K_{III}(t) = 2\tau_0 \sqrt{2c_s / \pi} \sqrt{t}.$$

For isotropic materials, the same expression for $K_{III}(t)$, with the shear wave velocity $c_s = \sqrt{\mu/\rho}$ is found.

Figure 3: (a) Stress intensity factor history $K_I(t)$ for a semi-infinite crack in different materials, real time. (b) Stress intensity factor history $K_I(t)$ and $K_{II}(t)$ for a semi-infinite crack in different materials. The isotropic case corresponds to epoxy and the orthotropic to graphite-epoxy.

4.1 Results and Conclusions

Closed form expressions of the dynamic stress intensity factors $K_I(t)$, $K_{II}(t)$ and $K_{III}(t)$ have been determined for semi-infinite cracks in orthotropic materials under the three loading

Figure 4: Comparison of the stress intensity factor $K_I(t)$ for a semi-infinite crack and a finite crack of length $2a$ in orthotropic material, the latter is a numerical solution obtained using integral transform methods in [3] and in [6] using FFT for Laplace transform inversion, $K_0 = \sigma_0 \sqrt{\pi a}$.

Table 1: Mechanical properties used for the analysis.

	Graphite Epoxy	E-Glass Epoxy	Boron Epoxy	Epoxy	Steel
c_{11}	20.77	8.38	32.67	3.91	3.5
c_{22}	2.18	2.29	3.12	3.91	3.5
c_{12}	0.49	0.52	0.79	1.91	1.5
μ_{12} (GPa)	7.48	5.5	6.4	1.96	76.92
ρ (Kg/m ³)	1600	2100	1990	1260	7840
$(c_{22}/c_{11})^{1/4}$	0.57	0.73	0.56	1	1

modes, i.e., opening, in-plane shear and antiplane shear loadings, respectively. The method of solution differs from that typically used in the isotropic case. The displacement formulation of the equations of motion is solved without the use of Helmholtz potentials. It has been shown that the orthotropic formulation includes the isotropic results as special cases. That is, for each loading mode the dynamic stress intensity factor for isotropic materials is recovered from the orthotropic expressions with the proper substitution of the elastic constants.

Fig. 3(a) shows the stress intensity factor history for the opening mode for different materials. The material properties used are shown in Table 1. As in the isotropic case, the stress intensity factors are proportional to the square root of time; hence there is no equivalent quasi-static problem for the semi-infinite crack under uniform loadings and there is no long-time equilibrium value. It can be seen that the fiber reinforcement of epoxy leads to an increase of the stress intensity factor for a given time, i.e., $K_I(t)$ for graphite-epoxy composite is greater than the corresponding $K_I(t)$ for epoxy at a given time t . Fig. 3(b) shows the stress intensity factors $K_I(t)$ and $K_{II}(t)$ for isotropic (epoxy) and orthotropic

(graphite-epoxy) materials, note that with same load amplitude the stress intensity factor $K_{II}(t)$ is greater than $K_I(t)$ at a given time. In both cases, the introduction of fibers results in an increase in the stress intensity factor.

It is interesting to note that $K_I(t)$ for a composite with fibers parallel to the x -axis and for a composite with fibers parallel to y -axis is the same. This result is contained in equation (31) since the ratio $\xi/\sqrt{c_{22}}$ is invariant to the replacement of c_{22} by c_{11} and c_{11} by c_{22} . This result does not hold for the in-plane shear loading however, since $K_{II}(t)$ for the fibers oriented along the y -axis is less than that for fibers oriented along the x -axis by a factor of $(c_{22}/c_{11})^{1/4}$. This factor is given in Table 1 for the materials examined here.

Integral transform methods have been applied to solve dynamic problems dealing with finite cracks in orthotropic materials. Fig. 4 shows the stress intensity factor for a finite crack of length $2a$ in orthotropic material under uniform impact loading, this is an approximated solution obtained by [3] and by [6] using a more suitable technique for numerical inversion of the Laplace transform. It is known that for short times the finite crack behaves like a semi-infinite crack. As illustrated in the figure, the closed form solution derived here agrees with the numerical solution for short times ($c_s t/a < 2$) as expected.

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